

**Robust and protective immune responses induced by heterologous
prime-boost vaccination with DNA-protein dimeric RBD vaccines for
COVID-19**

Short title: DNA vaccine candidate encoding RBD-dimer

Authors:

Yaling An^{a,1}, Gan Zhao^{b,1}, Huixin Duan^{a,1}, Ning Zhang^c, Minrun Duan^d, Senyu Xu^a,
Xueyuan Liu^e, Yuxuan Han^a, Tianyi Zheng^f, Xin Li^c, Jiawang Hou^b, Zhiyu Zhang^b,
Yuhai Bi^{c,g}, Xin Zhao^c, Kun Xu^h, Lianpan Dai^c, Bin Wang^{b*}, George F. Gao^{a,c,h*}

Affiliations:

^aSavaid Medical School, University of Chinese Academy of Sciences (UCAS), Beijing
101408, China;

^bAdvaccine Biopharmaceutics (Suzhou) Co. Ltd, Suzhou 215000, China;

^cCAS Key Laboratory of Pathogen Microbiology and Immunology, Institute of
Microbiology, Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS), Beijing 100101, China;

^dSchool of Life Sciences, Yunnan University, Kunming 650091, China

^eSchool of Public Health, Cheeloo College of Medicine, Shandong University, Jinan
250012, China;

^fZhejiang University School of Medicine, Hangzhou 310058, China;

^gCAS Center for Influenza Research and Early-Warning (CASCIRE), CAS-TWAS
Center of Excellence for Emerging Infectious Diseases (CEEID), Chinese Academy
of Sciences, Beijing 100101, China;

^hResearch Network of Immunity and Health (RNIH), Beijing Institutes of Life Science,
Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing 100101, China

¹These authors contributed equally to this work.

*Corresponding authors: bwang@advaccine.com (B.W.); gaof@im.ac.cn (G.F.G)

Abstract

The coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic posed great impacts on public health. To fight against the pandemic, robust immune responses induced by vaccination are indispensable. Previously, we developed a subunit vaccine adjuvanted by aluminum hydroxide, ZF2001, based on the dimeric tandem-repeat RBD immunogen, which has been approved for clinical use. This dimeric RBD design was also explored as an mRNA vaccine. Both showed potent immunogenicity. In this study, a DNA vaccine candidate encoding RBD-dimer was designed. The humoral and cellular immune responses induced by homologous and heterologous prime-boost approaches with DNA-RBD-dimer and ZF2001 were assessed in mice. Protection efficacy was studied by the SARS-CoV-2 challenge. We found that the DNA-RBD-dimer vaccine was robustly immunogenic. Priming with DNA-RBD-dimer followed by ZF2001 boosting induced higher levels of neutralizing antibodies than homologous vaccination with either DNA-RBD-dimer or ZF2001, elicited polyfunctional cellular immunity with a T_H1 -biased polarization, and efficiently protected mice against SARS-CoV-2 infection in the lung. This study demonstrated the robust and protective immune responses induced by the DNA-RBD-dimer candidate and provided a heterologous prime-boost approach with DNA-RBD-dimer and ZF2001.

Keywords: COVID-19, SARS-CoV-2, DNA vaccine, ZF2001, heterologous prime-boost immunization, immune responses

Introduction

COVID-19, caused by SARS-CoV-2, has resulted in more than 767 million cases, including more than six million deaths (WHO COVID-19 Dashboard) (1). The COVID-19 pandemic poses a great threat and challenge to public health globally. To fight against the pandemic, vaccine development has been initiated since the outbreak (2). The application of modern technologies, such as the mRNA vaccine, DNA vaccine, protein subunit vaccine, and adenovirus-vectored vaccine make the design and production of vaccine candidates available without obtaining the live virus (3). After the preclinical and clinical studies, some vaccine candidates were demonstrated to be safe, immunogenic, and effective, and thereafter were approved for emergency use (4, 5).

Due to the advantages of high immunogenicity, simple production, stability, and no anti-vector responses, several DNA vaccine candidates against COVID-19 have been developed and studied (6, 7). One DNA vaccine candidate contained ectodomain of S-protein (1-1213) with a trimeric foldon tag at the C-terminus and 6P mutations (F817P, A892P, A899P, A942P, K986P, V987P) induced neutralizing antibody (NAb) responses in mice (8). ZyCoV-D, INO-4800, and pSARS2-S, carrying the SARS-CoV-2 spike gene, induced protective immune responses in animals (9-11). COVID-eVax, encoding secreted monomeric SARS-CoV-2 RBD, induced stronger antibody responses than DNA vaccine candidates encoding full-length S protein and S1 subunit protein(12). COVID-eVax has been demonstrated to confer mice and ferrets substantial protection against the SARS-CoV-2 challenge (12).

In Phase 1 and 2 clinical trials, both ZyCoV-D and INO-4800 showed well-tolerated and immunogenic in participants, with induction of both humoral and cellular immune responses (13-15). In Phase 3 clinical trials, three doses of ZyCoV-D vaccine, administered intradermally via a needle-free injection system and separated by 28-day intervals, conferred 66.6% protection efficacy during the wave of Delta variant (16). Currently, ZyCoV-D vaccine has received emergency use authorization in India.

Previously, we developed the protein subunit vaccine, ZF2001, based on the SARS-CoV-2 RBD-dimer immunogen (17, 18). In the clinical trials, the ZF2001 vaccine induced robust humoral immune responses and balanced cellular immunity (19). The protection efficacies against symptomatic COVID-19 in the short-term (~50 days) and long-term (6 months) follow-ups were 81.4% and 75.7%, respectively (20). Recently, we turned this dimeric tandem RBD design into mRNA vaccines and showed high protective immunogenicity (21, 22).

It was demonstrated that both humoral and cellular immunity are critical for preventing COVID-19 (23-25). Although vaccination of ZF2001 induced high levels of NAbs, the induced cellular immunity was not potent due to the aluminum hydroxide adjuvant. However, it is advantageous for DNA vaccines to elicit robust cellular immune responses (7). In addition, we participated in the studies of INO-4800 DNA vaccine developments in early 2020. Therefore, we sought to combine the RBD-dimer immunogen and DNA delivery platform and further investigate the immune responses and protection efficacy by homologous or heterologous immunization with DNA vaccine encoding RBD-dimer and protein subunit vaccine ZF2001.

Results

Design and characterization of DNA vaccine encoding RBD-dimer

We designed and produced a recombinant DNA vaccine encoding tandem-repeat RBD-dimer of SARS-CoV-2 with a pVAX1 vector (Fig 1A). The backbone plasmid pVAX1, used in the INO-4800 vaccine and others, has safety records in various clinical trials (14, 15). The recombinant DNA vaccine candidate DNA-RBD-dimer was transfected into HEK293T cells, then the antigen protein expression was confirmed by western blot. The results showed that RBD-dimer was expressed and secreted from cells in a dose-dependent manner, with the expected molecular size in the membrane (Fig. 1B and 1C).

Humoral immune responses in mice

Groups of BALB/c mice (n = 8) were immunized to monitor the dynamic changes in antibody titers. These mice were immunized with two doses: (1) aluminum hydroxide adjuvant control; (2) empty vector pVAX1 control; (3) homologous protein subunit vaccine ZF2001; (4) homologous DNA-RBD-dimer; or (5) heterologous DNA-RBD-dimer>ZF2001, respectively, on Days 0 and 21 (Fig. 2). Murine sera were collected on Days 2, 4, 7, 14, 21, and 35. The RBD-dimer-binding IgG titers were measured by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). We observed that protein vaccine ZF2001 induced substantial humoral immune responses on Day 7, and then the IgG titers continuously increased (Fig. 2C). Interestingly, the antibody responses induced by the DNA vaccine were weak on Day 7 but sharply increased to high levels on Day 14 (Fig. 2D and 2E). The protein vaccine can be directly processed and presented after immunization. By contrast, the DNA plasmid must enter the cell nucleus and be transcribed into mRNA, which translates antigen protein in the cytoplasm. Then, both cellular and humoral immune responses were elicited (7). Therefore, the antibody responses were induced by the protein vaccine with a shorter period (7 days) than the DNA vaccine. DNA vaccine could induce potent antibody responses on Day 14.

Additionally, we observed that boosting with protein vaccine ZF2001 strongly enhanced the antibody responses on Day 35 (Fig. 2C and 2E).

Next, we immunized another batch of BALB/c mice (n = 12) to assess the serological neutralizing activities against a panel of vesicular stomatitis virus (VSV)-based pseudotyped viruses displaying SARS-CoV-2 S proteins from the prototype, Alpha, Beta, Delta, and Omicron (BA.1, BA.2, BA.2.12.1, and BA.4/5) variants of concern (VOCs). We found that heterologous immunization of DNA-RBD-dimer>ZF2001 elicited the highest NAb GMTs against the prototype and all the VOCs, compared with the two-dose homologous immunization with DNA-RBD-dimer or ZF2001 (Fig. 3). In particular, mice received heterologous DNA-RBD-dimer>ZF2001 immunization generated neutralizing antibody with geometric mean titers of 4464 for prototype pseudovirus, followed by 2372, 1963, 1298, 515, 505, 317, and 185 for Alpha, Beta, Delta, Omicron BA.1, BA.2, BA.2.12.1, and BA.4/5, respectively (Fig. 3). In addition, the NAb activities against Alpha and Omicron BA.1 between DNA-RBD-dimer>ZF2001 group and the two-dose homologous DNA-RBD-dimer group were significantly different (Fig. 3B and 3E). The Omicron BA.5 VOCs circulated globally, which showed severe immune escape to the previously authorized vaccines-induced humoral immune responses (26). Here, we observed that mice which received heterologous DNA-RBD-dimer>ZF2001 vaccinations developed NAb activities against BA.4/5 pseudovirus with a titer of 185, significantly higher than the titers 23 and 69 in the homologous ZF2001 and DNA-RBD-dimer groups, respectively (Fig. 3H).

Cellular immune responses in mice

To characterize the vaccine-induced cellular immune responses in the above-mentioned immunized mice, single suspensions of splenocytes were prepared from

spleens of mice 14 days post the second dose vaccination. Both enzyme-linked immunospot assay (ELISpot) and intracellular cytokines staining (ICS) were conducted. The ELISpot results showed that following stimulation with a peptide pool covering the SARS-CoV-2 RBD, splenocytes from mice received two-dose homologous DNA-RBD-dimer produced high levels of the T-help-1 (T_H1) cytokines (IFN γ and IL-2), and lower levels of T-helper-2 (T_H2) cytokine (IL-4) (Fig. 4A). For the homologous ZF2001 vaccination group, no obvious IFN γ , IL-2, and IL-4 cytokine secretion was observed (Fig. 4A). However, mice from the heterologous prime-boost groups significantly induced cellular immune responses by producing IFN γ and IL-2, though their levels were lower than those in the homologous DNA-RBD-dimer group (Fig. 4A).

The results of ICS suggested that homologous DNA-RBD-dimer immunization elicited the highest IFN γ , TNF- α and IL-2 secreting CD4 $^+$ and CD8 $^+$ T cells among all groups (Fig. 4B and 4C). Remarkably, the cytotoxic T lymphocyte (CTL) was robustly induced (Fig. 4B). The cellular immune responses induced by two doses of DNA-RBD-dimer were biased to T-help-1 (T_H1) polarization (Fig. 4B and 4C). Consistent with the ELISpot results, we observed that no apparent T cell responses were induced by homologous ZF2001 vaccine immunization (Fig. 4B and 4C). In comparison, the average levels of IFN γ , TNF- α and IL-2 T cells (CD4 $^+$ and CD8 $^+$) in the DNA-RBD-dimer>ZF2001 group were higher than those in the homologous ZF2001 group and lower than those in the homologous DNA-RBD-dimer group, which also exhibited a T_H1 -dominant response (Fig. 4B and 4C).

These ELISpot and ICS results revealed that both heterologous DNA and ZF2001 vaccines immunization strategy elicited antigen-specific and polyfunctional T cell responses biased to T_H1 profile.

Protection efficacy against SARS-CoV-2 challenge

To evaluate the protection efficacy by homologous and heterologous vaccination with DNA-RBD-dimer and ZF2001, SARS-CoV-2 (hCoV-19/China/CASB001/2020,

GISAID No. EPI_ISL_514256-7) challenge was performed. Serological NAbS against prototype S protein pseudovirus were measured and showed GMTs of 3440 and 2857 in the two-dose homologous ZF2001 and DNA-RBD-dimer groups, respectively, and GMT of 9685 in the heterologous DNA-RBD-dimer>ZF2001 group (Fig. 5A). Five days before the virus challenge, the BALB/c mice were transduced with the recombinant type 5 adenovirus expressing human ACE2 (Ad5-hACE2) to generate the sensitive mouse infection model (27, 28). Five days post SARS-CoV-2 challenge, these mice were euthanized and necropsied, and lung samples were collected for virus titration.

Both SARS-CoV-2 genomic RNA (gRNA) and sub-genomic RNA (sgRNA) were measured by qRT-PCR. Because viral sgRNA was generated during the virus replication in host cells, the levels of sgRNA correlate with the titers of live virus. In the aluminum hydroxide control group, high levels of viral RNA were detected with gRNA of 6.77×10^9 copies/g and sgRNA of 5.54×10^8 copies/g (Fig. 5B and 5C). In the empty vector group, similar levels of viral RNA were observed with gRNA of 1.51×10^9 copies/g (Fig. 5B). All the homologous and heterologous prime-boost vaccinated mice groups showed significantly reduced lung viral loads by more than 1000-fold (Fig. 5B). Especially, the gRNA of homologous ZF2001 and heterologous DNA-RBD-dimer>ZF2001 groups were 1.76×10^5 and 2.13×10^5 copies/g, respectively, which were lower than the gRNA of 1.45×10^6 copies/g in homologous DNA-RBD-dimer group (Fig. 5B). In addition, sgRNAs were not detected in the homologous ZF2001 and heterologous immunization groups but were detected in one out of four mice from the homologous DNA-RBD-dimer group (Fig. 5C). Therefore, these results indicated that heterologous DNA-RBD-dimer>ZF2001 provided complete protection against SARS-CoV-2 *in vivo*.

Discussion

In this study, we evaluated the immune responses and protection efficacy by homologous and heterologous immunization of DNA vaccine encoding RBD-dimer and protein subunit vaccine ZF2001. The results indicated that the levels of humoral immune responses in mice induced by the heterologous vaccination with DNA-RBD-dimer>ZF2001 were higher than those induced by homologous DNA-RBD-dimer or ZF2001 vaccination. More importantly, T cell response plays a crucial role in preventing COVID-19 (25). The cellular immunity induced by the early-approved COVID-19 vaccines was demonstrated to be broadly cross-reactive against the SARS-CoV-2 variants (29, 30). Compared with the weak cellular immune responses induced by two doses of ZF2001 vaccine, heterologous vaccination with DNA-RBD-dimer>ZF2001 elicited potent and multifunctional T_H1 cellular immune responses. The SARS-CoV-2 challenge study demonstrated that heterologous DNA-RBD-dimer>ZF2001 vaccination efficiently protected mice against SARS-CoV-2 infection in the lung. Most reported COVID-19 DNA vaccines and candidates encode spike, S1, or RBD protein (31-33). In the context of the continuous circulation of SARS-CoV-2, this study provided a new DNA vaccine candidate and a heterologous prime-boost approach with potent immunogenicity to expand the vaccine development pipeline. In this sense, this piece of work showed the privilege of DNA prime for the cellular response, better than the current protein prime.

DNA vaccine immunization was able to elicit innate immunity, cell-mediated responses, and prime antigen-specific antibody-secreting and memory B cells. Moreover, protein-boosting further elicits the humoral responses to secret high levels of valid antibody (34-36). The heterologous DNA-prime-protein-boost vaccination strategy was widely studied as a universal prime-boost approach to prevent infectious diseases (37, 38). Therefore, the protein-prime-DNA-boost group was not included in this study.

In the field of human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) vaccine development, heterologous DNA-prime-protein-boost regimens showed promising results (39-41). Particularly, Shan Lu's team conducted a series of studies on the heterologous prime-boost approach. They demonstrated that polyvalent gp120 DNA-prime-protein-boost HIV vaccine induced broader reactive neutralizing antibodies than protein-only vaccination approach in rabbits (42, 43). Then, they further conducted a phase I clinical trial in healthy adult volunteers, and found that polyvalent DNA-prime-protein-boost HIV vaccine (DP6-001) induced neutralizing activities to multiple HIV-1 subtypes, broad ADCC responses, durable gp120-specific memory B cells, and poly-functional T cell responses (35, 44).

To prevent the SARS-CoV-2, Li et al. reported that heterologous immunization with a DNA vaccine encoding SARS-CoV-2 S protein and followed by a recombinant subunit S1 protein vaccine induced robust neutralizing antibodies and cellular immune responses in rabbit and nonhuman primate models. In addition, they found that the co-delivery of DNA and protein vaccine components at the same time robustly induced the humoral immune responses and provided rhesus macaques complete protection against SARS-CoV-2 (45). Monoclonal antibodies isolated from rabbits received COVID-19 DNA vaccine encoding RBD followed by boosting with S1 protein vaccine showed potent neutralization capability against SARS-CoV-2 (46).

In addition, Wang et al. demonstrated that *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* ESAT6 DNA-prime-protein-boost vaccination significantly induced antibodies and T_H1-type cellular response in mice, which are essential for protection against TB infection (47). Ruitenber et al. reported that mice immunized with heterologous equine herpesvirus 1 (EHV-1) glycoprotein D (gD) DNA plus protein had enhanced humoral immune responses and had accelerated clearance of EHV-1 from lungs following challenge, compared with mice immunized with DNA or protein only (48). Consistent with the reported studies, we found that heterologous DNA-prime-protein-boost elicited stronger cellular immune responses (T_H1-biased) than those induced by two doses of

ZF2001 immunization. The heterologous approach is likely to elicit memory immune cells and enhances long-term protection.

One limitation of this study is the use of Ad5-hACE2-transduced mouse model. The neutralizing antibody GMT of heterologous DNA-RBD-dimer>ZF2001 group was higher than GMT of the homologous ZF2001 group (Fig. 5A). In addition, immunization with heterologous DNA-RBD-dimer>ZF2001 induced stronger cellular immune responses than two doses of ZF2001 vaccine. However, the protection efficacies between the heterologous prime-boost group and homologous ZF2001 group were similar, observed from the study with the transient transduction of Ad5-hACE2 mouse model (Fig. 5B and 5C). In these two groups, no pulmonary viral sgRNA was detected. Though pulmonary viral gRNA was detected, it was largely reduced to low levels, which was presumably the challenge virus. In addition, we did not observe progressive weight loss and lethality in the control groups. These are the limitations of the Ad5-hACE2-transduced mouse model.

The published studies demonstrated that DNA vaccines strongly elicited innate immunity through multiple pathways (36) and cellular immunity (40). It is likely that the heterologous DNA/protein prime/boost immunization enhances the somatic hypermutation and affinity maturation of B cells to generate antibodies with high affinity and diversity, resulting in broader activities against the SARS-CoV-2 variants, compared to the homologous immunization (34, 49). This mechanism is worth exploring in depth in our further studies.

Several immunization strategies have been explored for DNA vaccine immunization. Intramuscular injection of DNA vaccine has been demonstrated to induce protective immune responses (31, 50). Furthermore, INO-4800 is intradermally injected followed by electroporation with the CELLECTRA device. A controlled electric field is generated at the injection site to enhance the cellular uptake of the DNA plasmid (15). Similar approach with injection and electroporation was used by the other studies on DNA vaccines (8, 10, 12). In addition, the authorized DNA vaccine ZyCoV-D is intradermally

immunized via a needle-free injection system with a Pharmajet Tropis device, which generates a stream of pressurized fluid penetrating the skin at high velocity contributing to uniform dispersion and efficient uptake of DNA molecules (16, 51).

DNA vaccines could be designed and generated rapidly, applicable to mass production at low cost and induce robust immune responses without anti-vector responses. The clinical trial results of DNA vaccine candidate INO-4800 showed safety and immunogenicity in participants (14, 15). ZF2001 is a protein subunit vaccine, which has been approved for use in China and some other countries (20). Here, a heterologous vaccination approach was developed by priming with DNA-RBD-dimer followed by ZF2001 administration. The advantages of the DNA-RBD-dimer and ZF2001 were combined, which gives another choice for vaccination to fight against the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic.

Materials and Methods

Rare codon analysis and construction of DNA vaccine

The sequence of prototype SARS-CoV-2 (2019-nCoV strain IVDC-HB-01/2019, GISAID: EPI_ISL_402119) RBD-dimer was optimized with the GenScript Rare Codon Analysis Tool (<https://www.genscript.com/tools/rare-codon-analysis>) and coupled with an in-house analytic tool. The gene coding signal peptide and SARS-CoV-2 RBD-dimer was cloned into the pVAX1 vector (Invitrogen™, V26020), forming the DNA-RBD-dimer plasmid.

Plasmid preparation

Plasmids of DNA-RBD-dimer and pVAX1 were transformed into HB101 E. Coli, respectively. A single colony was undergone expansion in a one-liter flask for culturing in LB broth. Plasmids were extracted, purified by MaxPure Plasmid EF Giga Kit (Magen, China), and dissolved in saline buffer at the final concentration at 1 mg/mL. The purity was measured by an agarose gel electrophoresis and a UV detector at a range of 1.8-2.0 OD 260 nm/280 nm. Endotoxin in those plasmids was below 30 EU/mg by the LAL test.

Western blot

HEK293T cells were pre-plated in a six-well plate, followed by transfection with DNA-RBD-dimer vaccine or empty vector pVAX1 as a sham control. Forty-eight hours post transfection, cells were lysed, and culture supernatants were collected. Protein samples were separated by YongePAGE (Bis-Tris, 10x8, 4-12% gels) and analyzed by Western blotting with rabbit anti-RBD SARS-CoV-2 polyclonal antibodies. Goat anti-rabbit IgG-horseradish peroxidase (HRP) antibodies were used as a secondary antibody. The membranes were developed by the SuperSignal West Pico chemiluminescent substrate (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA).

Animal experiment

Female BALB/c mice (6-8 weeks of age) were purchased from Beijing Vital Laboratory Animal Technology Co., Ltd. (Beijing, China). They were housed under SPF conditions in the laboratory animal facilities at the Institute of Microbiology, Chinese Academy of Science (IMCAS). The challenge studies with prototype SARS-CoV-2 were conducted under the animal biosafety level 3 (ABSL3) facility in IMCAS. The mice experiments were approved by the Committee on the Ethics of Animal Experiments of the IMCAS, and performed in compliance with the recommendations in the Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals of the IMCAS Ethics Committee.

The 25 µg of DNA-RBD-dimer vaccine were administered to the tibialis anterior (TA) muscle by needle injection followed by CELLECTRA®2000 *in vivo* electroporation (EP) with two sets of pulses with 0.2 Amp constant current. The 10 µg of ZF2001 vaccine was performed by intramuscular injection. All vaccines were primed at day 0 and boosted at day 21, respectively. Blood samples were collected as described in the figure legends.

ELISA

ELISA was conducted to measure the antigen-specific antibody titers. Briefly, 96-well plates were coated with 3 µg/mL of RBD-dimer protein at 4°C overnight and blocked with 5% skim milk in PBST (0.05% Tween 20 in PBST) at 37°C for 1 hour. The plates were incubated with diluted murine serum for 2 hours at 37°C. The plates were incubated with goat anti-mouse IgG-HRP antibody (Abcam, ab6789) and then developed with 3,3',5,5'-tetramethylbenzidine (TMB) substrate. Reactions were stopped with 2 M of H₂SO₄, and measured at 450 nm using a microplate reader (PerkinElmer, USA).

Pseudovirus neutralization assay

The heat-inactivated (56°C for 30 minutes) murine sera were 2-fold serially diluted and incubated with pseudotyped viruses at 37°C for 1 hour. Then the mixture was transferred to pre-plated Vero-E6 cells in 96-well plates. After incubation for 15 hours, the transducing unit numbers were calculated on a CQ1 confocal image cytometer (Yokogawa). Fifty percent pseudovirus neutralization titer (pVNT₅₀) was determined by fitting nonlinear regression curves using GraphPad Prism and calculating the reciprocal of the serum dilution required for 50% neutralization of infection. pVNT₅₀ below the limit of detection was determined as half the limit of detection.

ELISpots

Spleens from mice were collected. Single suspended splenocytes were isolated and suspended in RPMI1640 media supplemented with 10% FBS and penicillin/streptomycin. ELISpot assays were performed using the mouse IFN γ , IL-2 and IL-4 ELISpot kits (Mabtech) following the manufacturer's instructions. Single suspension of splenocytes at 500,000 from each mouse were plated into each well coated with anti-mouse IFN γ , IL-2 or IL-4 antibodies and stimulated with a peptide pool (10 μ g/mL) covering the SARS-CoV-2 RBD for 36 hours at 37°C in a CO₂ incubator. The plates were processed in turn with a biotinylated detection antibody, streptavidin-ALP conjugate. Spots were quantified by ELISpot Reader (AID, Straßberg, Germany).

Intracellular cytokine stain (ICS)

The murine splenocytes were stimulated with the peptide pool (10 μ g/mL) and simultaneously treated with GolgiStop (BD Biosciences, USA). After 9 hours of incubation, the cells were harvested and stained with anti-CD3 (BioLegend), anti-CD4 (BioLegend) and anti-CD8 α (BioLegend) surface markers. The cells were subsequently fixed and permeabilized in permeabilizing buffer (BD Biosciences, USA) and stained with anti-IFN γ (BioLegend), anti-TNF α (BioLegend), anti-IL-2 (BioLegend)

and anti-IL4 (BioLegend) antibodies. All fluorescent lymphocytes were analyzed on BD LSRIIFortessa flow cytometer (BD Biosciences, USA).

SARS-CoV-2 challenge study

For the challenge experiment, a recombinant adenovirus Ad5-hACE2 transducing BALB/c mice model was used. Immunized BALB/c mice were intranasally infected with 8×10^9 vp of Ad5-hACE2. Five days later, the transduced mice were infected with 5×10^5 TCID₅₀ of SARS-CoV-2 (hCoV-19/China/CASB001/2020, GISAID: EPI_ISL_514256-7) via the intranasal route. The mice were euthanized and necropsied 5 days after the challenge. Lung tissues were collected for virus titration.

qRT-PCR

Mice lung tissues were weighed and homogenized. Viral RNA was isolated from 50 μ L supernatants of homogenized tissues using a nucleic acid extraction instrument MagMAX™ Express Magnetic Particle Processor (Applied Biosystems, USA). SARS-CoV-2 specific quantitative reverse transcription-PCR (qRT-PCR) assays were performed by using a FastKing One Step Probe RT-qPCR kit (Tiangen Biotech, China) on a CFX96 Touch real-time PCR detection system (Bio-Rad, USA) according to the manufacturer's protocol. Two sets of primers and probes were used to detect the N gene of viral gRNA and the E gene of sgRNA from SARS-CoV-2, respectively, with sequences as follows:

gRNA-F, GACCCCAAATCAGCGAAAT;

gRNA-R, TCTGGTACTGCCAGTTGAATCTG;

gRNA-probe, FAM-ACCCCGCATTACGTTTGGTGGACC-TAMRA (where FAM is 6-carboxyfluorescein, and TAMRA is 6-carboxytetramethylrhodamine);

sgRNA-F, CGATCTCTTGATAGATCTGTTCTC;

sgRNA-R, ATATTGCAGCAGTACGCACACA;

sgRNA-probe, FAM-ACACTAGCCATCCTTACTGCGCTTCG-TAMRA.

Viral loads were expressed on a \log_{10} scale as viral copies/gram after calculation with a standard curve. Viral copy numbers below the limit of detection were set as half of the limit of detection.

Statistics

Pseudotyped virus neutralization titers (pVNT₅₀) were determined by fitting nonlinear regression curves using GraphPad Prism and calculating the reciprocal of the serum dilution required for 50% neutralization of infection.

All the *P* values were analyzed with two-tailed Mann-Whitney test (ns, $p > 0.05$; * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$; **** $p < 0.0001$). Details can be found in figure legends.

Graphs were generated with GraphPad Prism software.

Acknowledgments

This work is supported by the National Key R&D Program of China (2020YFA0907100 and 2021YFC2302500), the National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC) (82041048, 81991494, 81991492 and 82041039) and a grant from the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation (INV-027420). L.D. is supported by the Excellent Young Scientist Program from NSFC (82122031) and the Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS) (YSBR-010). We thank all the staff of ABSL-3 at the Institute of Microbiology, CAS for their assistance of the experiments performed in ABSL-3. We are grateful to Tong Zhao in the Institute of Microbiology, CAS for her technical assistance with flow cytometry experiments.

Author Contribution Statement

G.F.G., B.W. and L.D. conceived the project and designed the experiments. Y.A., G.Z., H.D., N.Z., M.D., S.X., X.L., Y.H., T.Z., X.L., J.H. and Z.Z. performed the experiments. Y.B. supervised the experiments with SARS-CoV-2 in ABSL-3. Y.A., N.Z., S.X., Y.H. and T.Z. conducted the mice challenge experiments. X.Z. supervised the preparation of SARS-CoV-2 pseudoviruses and neutralizing antibody titration. G.F.G., B.W., L.D., K.X. and G.Z. analyzed the data. K.X., G.Z., L.D. and Y.A. wrote the manuscript. G.F.G., B.W., L.D. and K.X. revised the manuscript.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available in the figures in the manuscript.

References

1. Tan W, Zhao X, Ma X, Wang W, Niu P, Xu W, et al. A novel coronavirus genome identified in a cluster of pneumonia cases - Wuhan, China 2019–2020. *China CDC Wkly.* 2020;2(4): 61-62.
2. Gao GF. Science-based COVID-19 vaccine development. *Natl Sci Rev.* 2021;8(10):nwab193.
3. Dai L, Gao GF. Viral targets for vaccines against COVID-19. *Nat Rev Immunol.* 2021;21(2):73-82.
4. Xu K, Dai L, Gao GF. Humoral and cellular immunity and the safety of COVID-19 vaccines: a summary of data published by 21 May 2021. *Int Immunol.* 2021;33(10):529-40.
5. Xu K, Fan C, Han Y, Dai L, Gao GF. Immunogenicity, efficacy and safety of COVID-19 vaccines: an update of data published by 31 December 2021. *Int Immunol.* 2022;34(12):595-607.
6. Lee J, Arun Kumar S, Jhan YY, Bishop CJ. Engineering DNA vaccines against infectious diseases. *Acta Biomater.* 2018;80:31-47.
7. Silveira MM, Moreira G, Mendonca M. DNA vaccines against COVID-19: Perspectives and challenges. *Life Sci.* 2021;267:118919.
8. Wang X, Rcheulishvili N, Cai J, Liu C, Xie F, Hu X, et al. Development of DNA vaccine candidate against SARS-CoV-2. *Viruses.* 2022;14(5).
9. Patel A, Walters JN, Reuschel EL, Schultheis K, Parzych E, Gary EN, et al. Intradermal-delivered DNA vaccine induces durable immunity mediating a reduction in viral load in a rhesus macaque SARS-CoV-2 challenge model. *Cell Rep Med.* 2021;2(10):100420.
10. Chai KM, Tzeng TT, Shen KY, Liao HC, Lin JJ, Chen MY, et al. DNA vaccination induced protective immunity against SARS CoV-2 infection in hamsters. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis.* 2021;15(5):e0009374.
11. Yadav PD, Kumar S, Agarwal K, Jain M, Patil DR, Maithal K, et al. Assessment of immunogenicity and protective efficacy of ZyCoV-D DNA vaccine candidates in Rhesus macaques against SARS-CoV-2 infection. *BioRxiv.* 2021;<https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.02.02.429480>.
12. Conforti A, Marra E, Palombo F, Roscilli G, Rava M, Fumagalli V, et al. COVID-eVax, an electroporated DNA vaccine candidate encoding the SARS-CoV-2 RBD, elicits protective responses in animal models. *Mol Ther.* 2022;30(1):311-26.
13. Momin T, Kansagra K, Patel H, Sharma S, Sharma B, Patel J, et al. Safety and Immunogenicity of a DNA SARS-CoV-2 vaccine (ZyCoV-D): Results of an open-label, non-randomized phase I part of phase I/II clinical study by intradermal route in healthy subjects in India. *EClinicalMedicine.* 2021;38:101020.
14. Tebas P, Yang S, Boyer JD, Reuschel EL, Patel A, Christensen-Quick A, et al. Safety and immunogenicity of INO-4800 DNA vaccine against SARS-CoV-2: A preliminary report of an open-label, Phase 1 clinical trial. *EClinicalMedicine.* 2021;31:100689.
15. Kraynyak KA, Blackwood E, Agnes J, Tebas P, Giffear M, Amante D, et al. SARS-CoV-2 DNA vaccine INO-4800 induces durable immune responses capable of being boosted in a Phase 1 open-label trial. *J Infect Dis.* 2022;225(11):1923-32.

16. Khobragade A, Bhate S, Ramaiah V, Deshpande S, Giri K, Phophle H, et al. Efficacy, safety, and immunogenicity of the DNA SARS-CoV-2 vaccine (ZyCoV-D): the interim efficacy results of a phase 3, randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled study in India. *Lancet*. 2022;399(10332):1313-21.
17. Dai L, Zheng T, Xu K, Han Y, Xu L, Huang E, et al. A universal design of betacoronavirus vaccines against COVID-19, MERS, and SARS. *Cell*. 2020;182(3):722-33 e11.
18. An Y, Li S, Jin X, Han JB, Xu K, Xu S, et al. A tandem-repeat dimeric RBD protein-based covid-19 vaccine zf2001 protects mice and nonhuman primates. *Emerg Microbes Infect*. 2022;11(1):1058-71.
19. Yang S, Li Y, Dai L, Wang J, He P, Li C, et al. Safety and immunogenicity of a recombinant tandem-repeat dimeric RBD-based protein subunit vaccine (ZF2001) against COVID-19 in adults: two randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled, phase 1 and 2 trials. *Lancet Infect Dis*. 2021;21(8):1107-19.
20. Dai L, Gao L, Tao L, Hadinegoro SR, Erkin M, Ying Z, et al. Efficacy and safety of the RBD-Dimer-based COVID-19 vaccine ZF2001 in adults. *N Engl J Med*. 2022;386(22):2097-111.
21. Han Y, An Y, Chen Q, Xu K, Liu X, Xu S, et al. mRNA vaccines expressing homo-prototype/Omicron and hetero-chimeric RBD-dimers against SARS-CoV-2. *Cell Res*. 2022.
22. Chen Q, Du P, Han Y, Ma X, Zhang R, Rong X, et al. Rapid evaluation of heterologous chimeric RBD-dimer mRNA vaccine for currently-epidemic Omicron sub-variants as booster shot after inactivated vaccine. *Biosaf Health*. 2023;5(2):89-100.
23. Feng S, Phillips DJ, White T, Sayal H, Aley PK, Bibi S, et al. Correlates of protection against symptomatic and asymptomatic SARS-CoV-2 infection. *Nat Med*. 2021;27(11):2032-40.
24. Gilbert PB, Montefiori DC, McDermott AB, Fong Y, Benkeser D, Deng W, et al. Immune correlates analysis of the mRNA-1273 COVID-19 vaccine efficacy clinical trial. *Science*. 2022;375(6576):43-50.
25. Moss P. The T cell immune response against SARS-CoV-2. *Nat Immunol*. 2022;23(2):186-93.
26. Zhao X, Zhang R, Qiao S, Wang X, Zhang W, Ruan W, et al. Omicron SARS-CoV-2 neutralization from inactivated and ZF2001 vaccines. *N Engl J Med*. 2022;387(3):277-80.
27. Hassan AO, Case JB, Winkler ES, Thackray LB, Kafai NM, Bailey AL, et al. A SARS-CoV-2 infection model in mice demonstrates protection by neutralizing antibodies. *Cell*. 2020;182(3):744-53 e4.
28. Sun J, Zhuang Z, Zheng J, Li K, Wong RL-Y, Liu D, et al. Generation of a broadly useful model for COVID-19 pathogenesis, vaccination, and treatment. *Cell*. 2020;182(3):734-43 e5.
29. Liu J, Chandrashekar A, Sellers D, Barrett J, Jacob-Dolan C, Lifton M, et al. Vaccines elicit highly conserved cellular immunity to SARS-CoV-2 Omicron. *Nature*. 2022;603(7901):493-6.
30. Tarke A, Coelho CH, Zhang Z, Dan JM, Yu ED, Methot N, et al. SARS-CoV-2 vaccination induces immunological T cell memory able to cross-recognize variants from Alpha to Omicron. *Cell*. 2022;185(5):847-59 e11.

31. Yu J, Tostanoski LH, Peter L, Mercado NB, McMahan K, Mahrokhian SH, et al. DNA vaccine protection against SARS-CoV-2 in rhesus macaques. *Science*. 2020;369(6505):806-11.
32. Smith TRF, Patel A, Ramos S, Elwood D, Zhu X, Yan J, et al. Immunogenicity of a DNA vaccine candidate for COVID-19. *Nat Commun*. 2020;11(1):2601.
33. Alluhaybi KA, Alharbi RH, Alhabbab RY, Aljehani ND, Alamri SS, Basabrain M, et al. Cellular and humoral immunogenicity of a candidate DNA vaccine expressing SARS-CoV-2 spike subunit 1. *Vaccines (Basel)*. 2021;9(8).
34. Li H, Wang S, Hu G, Zhang L, Liu S, Lu S. DNA priming immunization is more effective than recombinant protein vaccine in eliciting antigen-specific B cell responses. *Emerging Microbes Infect*. 2021;10(1):833-41.
35. Wang S, Yates NL, Pollara J, Voronin Y, Stanfield-Oakley S, Han D, et al. Broadly binding and functional antibodies and persisting memory B cells elicited by HIV vaccine PDPHV. *npj Vaccines*. 2022;7(1):18.
36. Suschak JJ, Wang S, Fitzgerald KA, Lu S. A cGAS-independent STING/IRF7 pathway mediates the immunogenicity of DNA vaccines. *J Immunol*. 2016;196(1):310-6.
37. Kardani K, Bolhassani A, Shahbazi S. Prime-boost vaccine strategy against viral infections: Mechanisms and benefits. *Vaccine*. 2016;34(4):413-23.
38. Lu S. Heterologous prime-boost vaccination. *Curr Opin Immunol*. 2009;21(3):346-51.
39. Richmond JF, Lu S, Santoro JC, Weng J, Hu SL, Montefiori DC, et al. Studies of the neutralizing activity and avidity of anti-human immunodeficiency virus type 1 Env antibody elicited by DNA priming and protein boosting. *J Virol*. 1998;72(11):9092-100.
40. Bansal A, Jackson B, West K, Wang S, Lu S, Kennedy JS, et al. Multifunctional T-cell characteristics induced by a polyvalent DNA prime/protein boost human immunodeficiency virus type 1 vaccine regimen given to healthy adults are dependent on the route and dose of administration. *J Virol*. 2008;82(13):6458-69.
41. Chen Y, Wang S, Lu S. DNA immunization for HIV vaccine development. *Vaccines (Basel)*. 2014;2(1):138-59.
42. Wang S, Pal R, Mascola JR, Chou TH, Mboudjeka I, Shen S, et al. Polyvalent HIV-1 Env vaccine formulations delivered by the DNA priming plus protein boosting approach are effective in generating neutralizing antibodies against primary human immunodeficiency virus type 1 isolates from subtypes A, B, C, D and E. *Virology*. 2006;350(1):34-47.
43. Vaine M, Wang S, Crooks ET, Jiang P, Montefiori DC, Binley J, et al. Improved induction of antibodies against key neutralizing epitopes by human immunodeficiency virus type 1 gp120 DNA prime-protein boost vaccination compared to gp120 protein-only vaccination. *J Virol*. 2008;82(15):7369-78.
44. Wang S, Kennedy JS, West K, Montefiori DC, Coley S, Lawrence J, et al. Cross-subtype antibody and cellular immune responses induced by a polyvalent DNA prime-protein boost HIV-1 vaccine in healthy human volunteers. *Vaccine*. 2008;26(8):1098-110.
45. Li Y, Bi Y, Xiao H, Yao Y, Liu X, Hu Z, et al. A novel DNA and protein combination COVID-19 vaccine formulation provides full protection against SARS-CoV-2 in rhesus macaques. *Emerg Microbes Infect*. 2021;10(1):342-55.

46. Chen Y, Zhu L, Huang W, Tong X, Wu H, Tao Y, et al. Potent RBD-specific neutralizing rabbit monoclonal antibodies recognize emerging SARS-CoV-2 variants elicited by DNA prime-protein boost vaccination. *Emerg Microbes Infect.* 2021;10(1):1390-403.
47. Wang Q-m, Sun S-h, Hu Z-l, Yin M, Xiao C-j, Zhang J-c. Improved immunogenicity of a tuberculosis DNA vaccine encoding ESAT6 by DNA priming and protein boosting. *Vaccine.* 2004;22(27-28):3622-7.
48. Ruitenberg KM, Walker C, Love DN, Wellington JE, Whalley JM. A prime-boost immunization strategy with DNA and recombinant baculovirus-expressed protein enhances protective immunogenicity of glycoprotein D of equine herpesvirus 1 in naïve and infection-primed mice. *Vaccine.* 2000;18(14):1367-73.
49. Abdollahi N, Jeusset L, de Septenville A, Davi F, Bernardes JS. Reconstructing B cell lineage trees with minimum spanning tree and genotype abundances. *BMC Bioinf.* 2023;24(1):70.
50. Tamming LA, Duque D, Tran A, Zhang W, Pfeifle A, Laryea E, et al. DNA based vaccine expressing SARS-CoV-2 spike-CD40L fusion protein confers protection against challenge in a syrian hamster model. *Front Immunol.* 2021;12:785349.
51. Dey A, Chozhavel Rajanathan TM, Chandra H, Pericherla HPR, Kumar S, Choonia HS, et al. Immunogenic potential of DNA vaccine candidate, ZyCoV-D against SARS-CoV-2 in animal models. *Vaccine.* 2021;39(30):4108-16.

Figures

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of DNA-RBD-dimer vaccine and antigen expression.

(A). Schematic diagram of DNA vaccine coding RBD-dimer. SP, signal peptide.

(B). HEK293T cells were transfected with empty pVAX1 (2.5 µg) or DNA-RBD-dimer (2.5 µg) plasmids. Antigen protein was probed in cell lysates and culture supernatants by western blot.

(C). Characterization of the antigen expression of the DNA-RBD-dimer vaccine in a dose-dependent manner. HEK293T cells were transfected with empty pVAX1 (5 µg) or DNA-RBD-dimer (0.05, 0.1, 0.25, 0.5, 1, 2.5, or 5 µg) plasmids. Antigen protein was probed in cell lysates and culture supernatants by western blot.

Fig. 2. The dynamic changes in antibody responses.

Female BALB/c mice at 6- to 8-week-old were randomly divided into five groups ($n = 8$). These mice were immunized with two doses: (1) aluminum hydroxide adjuvant control (A); (2) empty vector pVAX1 control (B); (3) homologous protein subunit vaccine ZF2001 (C); (4) homologous DNA-RBD-dimer (D); or (5) heterologous DNA-RBD-dimer>ZF2001 (E), respectively. Vaccine regimens were injected on Days 0 and 21. The RBD-dimer-binding IgG endpoint titers were analyzed by ELISA for sera samples collected on Days 2, 4, 7, 14, 21, and 35. The values are the GMTs. The horizontal dashed line indicates the limit of detection.

Fig. 3. Evaluation of the humoral immune responses by pseudotyped virus neutralization assays.

Female BALB/c mice at 6- to 8-week-old were randomly divided into five groups ($n = 12$). These mice were immunized with two doses: (1) aluminum hydroxide adjuvant control; (2) empty vector pVAX1 control; (3) homologous protein subunit vaccine ZF2001; (4) homologous DNA-RBD-dimer; or (5) heterologous DNA-RBD-dimer>ZF2001, respectively. Vaccine regimens were injected at a 21 days interval. Sera samples collected 14 days post the second dose immunization were tested for neutralization of a panel of pseudotyped viruses displaying SARS-CoV-2 prototype (A), Alpha (B), Beta (C), Delta (D) and Omicron BA.1 (E), BA.2 (F), BA.2.12.1 (G) and BA.4/5 (H) spikes. P values were analyzed with two-tailed Mann-Whitney test (ns, $P > 0.05$; * $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.001$; **** $P < 0.0001$). The values are the GMT \pm 95% confidence interval (CI). The horizontal dashed line indicates the limit of detection.

Fig. 4. Evaluation of the cellular immune responses by ELISpot and ICS.

Spleens of BALB/c mice were collected 14 days post the boost.

(A). ELISpot assays were performed to assess the IFN γ , IL-2 and IL-4 secretion of splenocytes after stimulation with peptides pool covering SARS-CoV-2 RBD.

(B). Quantification of the frequency of IFN γ , TNF- α , IL-2, and IL-4 producing CD8⁺ T cells of splenocytes by ICS.

(C). Quantification of the frequency of IFN γ , TNF- α , IL-2, and IL-4 producing CD4⁺ T cells of splenocytes by ICS.

Data are means \pm SEM. *P* values were analyzed with two-tailed Mann-Whitney test (ns, *P* > 0.05; **P* < 0.05; ***P* < 0.01).

Fig. 5. Protective efficacy against SARS-CoV-2.

Female BALB/c mice at 6- to 8-week-old were randomly divided into six groups (n = 6) and immunized with two doses of DNA-RBD-dimer, two doses of ZF2001, DNA-RBD-dimer followed by ZF2001, aluminum hydroxide adjuvant control and empty vector pVAX1 control, respectively. Vaccines were injected at a 21 days interval.

(A). Sera samples collected 14 days post the boost were tested for neutralization of pseudotyped viruses displaying SARS-CoV-2 prototype spike. The values are the GMT \pm 95% CI. The horizontal dashed line indicates the limit of detection.

(B, C). At 5 days post-Ad5-hACE2 transduction, mice were anesthetized and intranasally challenged with 5×10^5 TCID₅₀ SARS-CoV-2. Four mice were dead after anesthetization due to the misoperation. Animals were then euthanized and necropsied on 5 DPI and lung tissues were harvested for virus titration by qRT-PCR probing viral gRNA (B) and sgRNA (C). The horizontal dashed line indicates the limit of detection. Data are GMT \pm 95% CI. *P* values were analyzed with two-tailed Mann-Whitney test (ns, *P* > 0.05; ***P* < 0.01).